

THE VIEWS OF SCHOLARS ABOUT THE SEMANTIC FEATURES OF PHRASEOLOGY

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Abstract: This article explains the concepts of “field” and “semantic field” and their characteristics within phraseology in linguistics. It highlights the underexplored role of the “semantic field” concept in phraseology. Additionally, the article discusses various scholarly perspectives on semantic features in phraseology and explores how certain phraseological units have been interpreted.

Key words: field, contextual field, scope of concepts, semantic field, phraseological unit.

The actuality of studying the essence of the semantic features of phraseology in linguistics is significant due to its impact on understanding language structure and meaning. It addresses how phrases function in real-world communication, reflecting changes in language use and interpretation. This field is crucial for improving language processing technologies, enhancing translation accuracy. As language evolves, delving into phraseological semantic relationships remains essential for capturing contemporary linguistic dynamics and applications.

In linguistics, perspectives on semantic field theory focus on examining the meaning of words. Every aspect of the universe, including events and actions, is represented in the human mind as concepts. These concepts are conveyed through words within a sound system that maintains a cohesive sense of meaning. The essence of the semantic features of phraseology involves the study of how phrases and their meanings interact within a language. It delves into the relationships between phrases, their components, and how they convey meaning in different contexts. This field explores how phrases are constructed, their semantic roles, and how they contribute to the overall meaning in communication. The ultimate goal is to understand the underlying patterns and principles governing phrase usage and interpretation in various linguistic environments.

Researchers explain the term “contextual field” in various way. For example, I.Trir considers the “scope of concepts” as a semantic field and according to L.Weisgerber, it is a certain part of the content of a language, a component while G.Ipsen interpreted that it is a group of semantically and grammatically connected

words as a semantic field. A. Yolles called it “semantic unification”. The lexical structure of the language is separable the semantic field in the semantic groups that are considered by F.Dornzaif and V.Vartburg [2]. Above although researchers interpret the term contextual field differently, in understanding their internal form of language which is the basis of semantic research combining language with comprehensive and diverse learning possible.

In addition, this theory was expanded upon by Russian scholars such as G.S.Shur, A.A. Ufimseva, N.I.Filicheva, and Yu.N.Karaulov. A key development in the concept of “field” in linguistics was the work of L.Weisgerber, who argued that language is not merely a tool for conveying spiritual content but rather an intellectual framework for understanding the world, and that semantics should focus on the study of concepts rather than just meaning. V.Portsig introduced a specific concept of the semantic field, aiming to explain speech through this theoretical framework. Alongside V.Portsig, F.Yolles also offered a new perspective on the interpretation of fields in linguistics, demonstrating that these units, characterized by their integrative nature, belong to a particular group by reflecting various aspects of the whole.

G.Ipsen during his research comparative-historical study of the lexicon of ancient Indo European languages used the term semantic field initially while coining in Eastern languages applied to a group of words denoting nouns, which is one of those words in Indo-European languages it is functionally limited and forms that are based on a separate group. G.S.Shur further developed and analyzed the field theory and field types such as, paradigmatic field, syntactic field, functional-semantic field, associative of field, morpho-semantic field on the example of Russian language. According to the scientist, the lexical units in each language are invariant and functional-invariant groups, all of which are properties emerge through them. Thus, such groups can be considered a linguistic field [3].

At that time, researchers explained the term “semantic field” differently. For example, I.Trir defines “scope of concepts” as a semantic field while L.Weisgerber “means a certain part of the content of a language, a component” and Gipsen defined that a group of words that are semantically and grammatically connecting was interpreted as a semantic field. In addition to this, A.Yolles called it “semantic unification”. F. Dornzeif and W.Wartburg see the lexical structure of the semantic field in the semantic groups that exist separable [2].

On the problems of field theory in linguistics a number of works have been carried out in recent years. For example, F.I.Filichyova language argued about areas at the syntax level. As for the study of semantic fields, the study of the word in terms

of semantic fields was proposed in 1930 by the German linguist I. Trir. He published several works and articles over the years. In doing so, he thought from the point of view of understanding. According to him, each word enters the field of understanding and does not remain in the middle. The historical development of the word is the redistribution of a fixed area. I. Trir's theory of semantic fields was continued by his compatriot L. Weisgerber. In his view, language interprets objective existence differently through different languages. The meaning of a word is determined by which word group the word belongs to, that is, in which field it is located. I. Trir and L. Weisgerber evaluate the meaning of a word not from that word, but from the field of concepts. In addition, they promote the idealistic idea that the field of concepts does not change [1].

In current linguistic studies, phraseology is generally defined as a phraseological unit associated with a particular conceptual domain in the language, characterized by a unified semantic aspect but with specific differential and categorical meanings. This concept is viewed as a type of semantic field created by a collection of such units. Research on phraseological semantics, the semantic structure of these units, and the systematic organization of phraseology is undertaken by scholars such as Yu. Yu. Avaliani, N. F. Alefirenko, A. Birikh, S. G. Gavrin, Yu. A. Gvozdarev, V. P. Jukov, A. V. Kunin, A. M. Melerovich, N. A. Saburova, A. M. Emirova and among others. The phraseological field is understood as a set of phraseological units that are in a certain structural relationship and are combined with a common semantic theme and a common expression of a single concept. "Phraseological unit is a completely stable combination of words or partially revised meaning" [4].

In conclusion, the results from studies expressing these views indicate that the unique complexities of phraseological semantics drive this phenomenon. Consequently, it suggests that the semantic characteristics of phraseology should be viewed as a distinct microsystem, interconnected with both extralinguistic and linguistic aspects within the relevant lexical field.

References:

1. Mirtojdiyev M. O'zbek tili semasiologiyasi. – Toshkent: Mumtoz so'z, 2010. – P.11.
2. Vaqqosova D. O'zbek tilida anemonimlarning semantik tahlili: Filol.fanlari nomzodi... diss. avtoref. – Farg'ona, 2005. – 46 p.
3. Караулов Ю.Н. Общая русская идеография. – М: Наука, 1976. – С.42.
4. Кунин А.В. Фразеология современного английского языка. – М.: Международные отношения, 1972. – 210 с.